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D5.6: Report on demonstration at Demosite4: Omiš

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

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Executive summary

Deliverables D5.3, D5.4, D5.5 and D5.6 describe the demonstration activities related to water treatment at the four demonstration sites in Italy, Israel, Spain, and Croatia respectively, performed in task T5.3 “Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules” in WP5 “Demonstration of small loops of water recycling within a complex system”.

Deliverable D5.6 reports the results of the demo activities at Project Ô Demosite 4, carried out in Omis, Croatia, on the outlet waters of the biological treatment plant of the wastewaters generated in the textile company Galeb bb. Demo activities involve advanced tertiary treatments to reuse secondary treated WW. This deliverable stems from the content of D5.2 that describes the details of installation and validation of the PHOTO.NANOF pilot plant for water treatment.

The present report includes:

- an introduction to the demonstration site and to the set of water treatment technologies included in the PHOTO.NANOF water treatment module,
- the purpose of the PHOTO.NANOF modules, aimed to reuse secondary treated water in textiles baths. Waters of different quality and composition can be obtained, also allowing the partial reuse of dissolved salts,
- an overall description of demonstration activities undertaken,
- the results obtained during the demonstration activities.

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1 Abbreviations

AAU: Aalborg University
DOC: Dissolved Organic Carbon
ESI: ElectroSpray Interface
IRIS: IRIS S.r.l.
LOQ: Limit of Quantification
MDL: Method Detection Limit
MQL: Method Quantitation Limit
MRM: Multiple Reaction Monitoring (in mass spectrometry)
MW: Molecular Weight
NF: Nanofiltration
PAH: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
P&I: Piping and Instrumentation diagram
PHOTO.CAT: photocatalytic module for advanced tertiary treatment of water
PHOTO.NANOF: advanced tertiary treatment pilot plant combining Photocatalysis, Nanofiltration and Reverse Osmosis installed in Demosite 4
RO: Reverse Osmosis
SBSE: Stir Bar Sorptive Extraction
TN: Total Nitrogen
TOC: Total Organic Carbon
UNITO: Università degli Studi di Torino (Italy), Department of Chemistry
USP: Unique Selling Point
WW: Waste Water
WWTP: Waste Water Treatment Plant

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4 Introduction

"Water, water, everywhere, nor any drop to drink"

From *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*, S.T.Coleridge, 1798

The main objective of Project Ô is to develop and demonstrate a set of tools enabling circular use of water; among those tools there is a set of innovative technologies for water treatment characterized by high efficiency and low-cost processes, enabling the adoption of a modular approach. Moreover, in this Demosite the treatment train was developed to deliver a purified water with on-demand composition, enabling its reuse in the processing of textiles.

This document collects the activities carried out in Task 5.3 (Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules: running of pilot plants with collection of data for monitoring) regarding Demosite 4 in Omis (Croatia). The onsite demonstration and testing campaign was undertaken and resulted in the collection of operative data to evaluate the performance of the PHOTO.NANOF module. A summary of the four demonstration sites is reported in Table 1.

Demosite 1: Acquedotto Pugliese, Lecce – Italy. Mobile desalination + advanced Oxidation Process for treating contaminated brackish groundwater.
Demosite 2: National Center for Mariculture, Eilat - Israel. Polishing algae plant for water reuse in RAS pond + disinfected fresh water for aquaponic produced through nano-pulsed PEF, membrane distillation and advanced adsorption treatments.
Demosite 3: Almendralejo WWTP, Almendralejo – Spain. Mobile Advanced Adsorption and Photo Fenton with advanced control unit
Demosite 4: Galeb, Omis – Croatia. Photocatalytic module and nanofiltration to allow water reuse in textile industry

Table 1 Brief summary of the four demonstration sites

The table below summarises key features of Demosite 4, technologies and responsibilities for pilot scale module assembly and validation.

Demosite 4	Owner: Galeb
PHOTO.NANOF pilot plant	composed by: Photocatalytic Solar/LED module for TOC abatement (PHOTO.CAT by UNITO), nanofiltration and RO (NANOF by AAU) integrated with contributions from UNITO (Leads: UNITO)

Purpose	1) Non-biodegradable TOC load abatement with salt content retention; 2) hardness and multivalent ions elimination; 3) desalination; three water types are obtained, that can be mixed on demand to obtain the desired water composition, with partial recovery of salt (e.g., sodium sulfate from dyeing baths). Treated water is reused in dyeing and bleaching textile baths. Before pilot installation the Galeb company was using tap water as feed. PHOTO.NANOF is decreasing 20% the water footprint of the company.
Status	installed, validated, and fully operating. PHOTO.CAT Demonstration activities at 6 m ³ /day, NANOF: NF + RO water max 30 m ³ /day, for a total water production of 36 m ³ /day. Slightly lower than what planned by original DOA. This stems from the variation in Demosite 4 partner (original Olimpia SA, new Galeb dd m ³ /day), with relevant variations in needed water composition.

Table 2. Demosite 4 summary

5 DEMOSITE 4: Galeb dd company, Omis, Croatia

5.1 Location and rationale of the choice

The demonstration site is located in Omiš (Almissa), a town and port in the Dalmatia region of Croatia and is a municipality in the Split-Dalmatia County. The town is situated approximately 25 kilometres (16 miles) south-east of Croatia's second largest city, Split. Its location is where the Cetina River meets the Adriatic Sea. Galeb d.d. is a textile company with a factory placed in Omiš, Croatia, Punta 6, very near to Cetina River (Figure 1). Being part of the "Natura 2000" eco network, Galeb requires a high-level wastewater treatment, and, possibly, a reduction of the water footprint. This is one of the motivations of the choice of the location. Moreover, textiles production (including cotton farming) uses around 93 billion cubic metres of water annually, representing 4% of global freshwater withdrawal (World Bank, AQUASTAT, and FAO, Dataset: Annual freshwater withdrawals, total (2014)). Clothing accounts for over two thirds of this water use. In this respect, an urgent need of a decrease in its water footprint is highly desirable.

5.2 Water footprint at Demosite 4

At the Galeb dd plant, the textile processes of bleaching, dyeing, and washing require around 36 L, 210 L and 30 L of water per kg of knit/linen, respectively. The treated mass of knit/linen is around 1.8 metric ton/day, resulting in an average drinkable water consumption of 165 m³/day. The average water now discharged is 150 m³/day. Losses are mainly due to evaporation. Dyeing processes make use of high saline water (sodium sulphate around 5 g/L), so the spent waters from dyeing baths contain surfactants, residual dyes, and salts. The just realized WWTP biological plant, as secondary treatment, produces an outlet water with an average TOC content of 5-15 mg/L, from an average of 350-400 mg/L of the inlet mixed waste. The biological WWTP treat the mix of civil and textile wastewater in order to feed the bacteria with the proper ratio of nutrients. However, the secondary treated water has not a proper composition and purity to be reused. PHOTO.NANOF, with the three technologies implemented, allows a reuse of up to 20% of the textile processing water, with a partial reuse of sulfate salts.

Figure 1. Galeb dd Demosite 4.

5.3 The PHOTO.NANOF module

To decrease the discharge in the Cetina River of waters with high sulfate content (1-3 g/L) and decrease of at least 20% the water footprint of the Galeb dd plant, part of the outlet of the secondary

biological treatment will be processed by the tertiary treatments implemented in PHOTO.NANOF module (Figure 2). Flows reported are the maximum flows achieved during the demo activities. PHOTO.CAT flows were obtained with 24h operations, by using the backup UV LED source at night and in the absence of sufficient solar UV radiant power (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Scheme of the PHOTO.NANOF module and integration in the operation of the biological WWTP.

The plant is made of three sub-modules: two Nanofiltration units (NF) and the PHOTO.CAT unit. Those sub modules operate in parallel to obtain a water with the desired saline content, free of non-biodegradable TOC, to be reused in washing, dyeing or bleaching baths in the textile facility:

1. **Photocatalytic water purification reactor (PHOTO.CAT)** (Figure 3). This technology is able to completely mineralize non-biodegradable organic compounds (upper limit of TOC is of the order of 20 mg/L TOC, depending on the compounds), possibly with solar light and with no needs of added chemicals (but molecular oxygen). Another USP worth of note is the absence of waste, like in carbon adsorption, due to the complete mineralization of the pollutant load. Water inorganic constituents (e.g. saline content) are left unchanged.
2. **Nanofiltration (NF)** unit 1 and 2 (Figure 4) are equipped with innovative membranes, characterized by a distribution of pore sizes centred at the nanometre level, to remove salts and other pollutants (metals, organic contaminants, dissolved solids) from water matrices. NF1 is equipped with a membrane able to reject >98% of multivalent ions, so eliminating hardness and sulfate. NF2 is equipped with a membrane with lower pore size, able to reject multivalent ions and > 90% middle sized monovalent ions (chlorides).

Figure 3. PHOTO.CAT submodule during day and at night with UV LED powered at 20 W/m² radiant UV intensity.

Figure 4. NF1 and NF2 units. They are integrated in the same skid. The upper 3 cartridges are the NF1 sub-module (multivalent ions retention), the lower two cartridges the NF2 submodule (>90% chloride retention). In the upper photo, the control unit with PLCs can be seen. In the middle photo the inlet tank of NF2. In the lower photo the inlet tank of NF1. Inlet tanks can be bypassed if a continuous water feed is supplied.

6 Demonstration Activities and input water assessment

WP5 is directed to show the tools that allow water management in small loops, in terms of advanced technologies and impact evaluation tools: this also includes the demonstration activities reported in this deliverable. Whilst D5.2 reported the site preparation, the installation of the pilot plants and their operation, this document instead focuses on the demonstration activities and data collection at Demosite2.

PHOTO.NANOF module at Demosite 4 is integrated in the wastewater treatment facility of Galeb dd, located near the biological WWTP. PHOTO.CAT submodule is obviously installed outdoor. NF1 and NF2 are installed indoor in the control centre of the WWTP. All sub-modules can be remotely controlled via internet connection. The layout of the module is described in detail in D5.2. The purpose of the module is the treatment of output water of the biological WWTP to eliminate residual and non-biodegradable TOC and, if needed, salts (in particular sulfates) to drinking water quality. Waters treated with PHOTO.CAT, NF1 and NF2 are mixed as required for use in textiles baths. Besides water, also sulfates are recovered.

The average composition of the output water of the biological WWTP during the Demo activities, used as input water for PHOTO.NANOF, is reported in Table 3. The compositions are different from those reported in D2.1. At that time the biological WWTP was not operative, and the raw mixed WW were analysed. Besides TOC, TN and common ions, also the presence of 157 pesticides, bisphenol A, octyl and nonylphenols are determined during Demo activities (see list of pesticides and analytical conditions in the Appendix). The pesticides were analysed to assess water purity. Bisphenol A, octyl and nonylphenols are common contaminants of wastewaters from textile companies and can leak from biological WWTP (Robert Loos, Georg Hanke, Gunther Umlauf, Steven J. Eisenreich *Chemosphere* 66 (2007) 690–699). However, in all samples (inlet and treated) the 157 pesticides are in all samples below MQL and are not reported. Traces of bisphenol A and alkyl phenols are found in some inlet waters, but not in the waters treated with PHOTO.NANOF.

The Demo activities ran from August to November 2022 and are still running. Demonstration activities were also partially carried out at the pilots' manufacturers.

The PHOTO.CAT submodule is run in batch mode, filling the tank (see PHOTO.CAT scheme in Figure 5 and recirculating tank in Figure 6) with 1.2 m³ of water to be treated (sand filtered WWTP outlet). The water is recirculated between the tank and the photocatalytic panels till the concentration of dissolved oxygen at the outlet of the photocatalytic panel is at least 80% of the dissolved oxygen at the inlet (bulk of the recirculating tank). With the outlet water of the biological WWTP (5-15 mg/L TOC) treatment time is under 4 hours with 20 W/m² UV A total intensity). Demo activities of PHOTO.CAT are carried with LED backup sources on when solar UV A is under 20 W/m² (see Figure 3). With “solar only” working mode the electrical energy consumed per cubic meter purified is 1.50 kWh.

The NF1 and NF2 submodules are run in continuous mode. The two systems were set to work with a permeate/retentate ratio of 4/5 and 1/4 V/V, respectively. These were set in order to optimise energy consumption. NF1 and NF2 were also tested by using a high salinity ground water, extracted from a well underneath the Galeb site. The salinity is changing with the season, and it is due to sea water intrusion. Galeb dd could use this water in case of shortages of tap water. The composition is reported in Table 4.

Parameter	Value
pH	7.9
k (μS cm ⁻¹)	3675
TC (mg L ⁻¹)	30.4
IC (mg L ⁻¹)	21
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)	8.4
TN (mg L ⁻¹)	1
Chlorides (mg L ⁻¹)	65
Nitrates (mg L ⁻¹)	3.5

Posphates (mg L-1)	<0.1
Sulfates (mg L-1)	1270
Sodium (mg L-1)	610
Magnesium (mg L-1)	18
Calcium (mg L-1)	50
Bisphenol A, (ng/L)	35
octyl and nonylphenol, (ng/L)	120

Table 3. Average composition of biological WWTP outlet during Demo activities (August-November 2022)

Parameter	Value
pH	7.08
k ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	12240
TC (mg L^{-1})	52
IC (mg L^{-1})	48
TOC (mg L^{-1})	4
TN (mg L^{-1})	1.3
Chlorides (mg L-1)	3700
Nitrates (mg L-1)	< 2
Posphates (mg L-1)	< 2
Sulfates (mg L-1)	650
Sodium (mg L-1)	1800
Magnesium (mg L-1)	250
Calcium (mg L-1)	580

Table 4. Composition of the well water used in one test of NF1 and NF2

Figure 5. Scheme of the PHOTO.CAT submodule with the automatic controls and sensors

Figure 6. PHOTO.CAT recirculating tank.

7 Testing reports

7.1 PHOTO.CAT submodule

The PHOTO.CAT submodule is run in batch mode. The operations are remotely controlled, including filling and discharge of the tank through discharge and load ball valves (see Figure 6). In Figure 7 is reported the remote-control console of PHOTO.CAT. During operation in Galeb, the purified water is directed into a storage tank, to be utilized in the washing or dyeing baths after mixing with NF1 – NF2 output as required to adjust composition.

Testing activities started before installation at the demosite, at the pilot’s manufacturers, and were carried out by using a synthetic wastewater with TOC, TC, sulfates, hardness similar to WWTP outlet. TOC was composed by Brij 35 nonionic surfactant. These data were presented in D5.2.

PHOTO.CAT Ver 1.3

Operations: Modify config, calibration, working parameters file

Message

Manual control

VISA resource name: COM4 Save Save time (hh:mm:ss): 00:01:00

pH (-): 8.46	T (°C): 28.7	Level (m): 0.95	UV (W/m ²): 30.35	ORP (mV): 34.61	O2 pre-treatment (mg/l): 37.04	Cond low (µS/cm): 102.88
					O2 post-treatment (mg/l): 30.58	Cond high (µS/cm): 409.35

Manual control

Activate pump Pump ON

Activate oxygenator Oxygenator ON

Open valve inlet Fill request Valve in OPEN

Ready to discharge Discharge ready Discharge ACK

Activate discharge pump Discharge pump ON

Led manual control Led power

Status LED OFF

Solar mode only

User intervention required LED Booster stop STOP

Panels

Figure 7. Remote control console of PHOTO.CAT submodule.

In Galeb dd the Demo activities were carried out on the water before and after treatment for each batch, with a maximum of 5 batches of 1.2 m³ per day (average of 6 m³ of purified water per day). However, to completely assess the capabilities of the apparatus, for two days a complete profile of the TOC decays was done: in Figure 8 are reported the time profiles of TOC decay registered during Demo activities on 7 September 2022 treating biological WWTP outlet. In Figure 9 the same profiles registered in day 12 October 2022. TOC profiles reveal a smooth TOC degradation and mineralization to CO₂.

Figure 8. Time profiles of TOC during batch treatment of WWTP outlet in PHOTO.CAT submodule in Omis, 7 September 2022

Figure 9. Time profiles of TOC during batch treatment of WWTP outlet in PHOTO.CAT submodule in Omis, 12 October 2022

For each 1.2 m³ treated, the water composition before and after treatment are measured by UNITO. Parameters measured are reported in Table 3. As stated before, also the 157 pesticides reported in Appendix are determined but the concentrations are always under the LOQ.

The parameters affected by the treatment are only the TOC, including non-biodegradable organic pollutants. In the input waters are detected bisphenol A and alkylphenols at concentration levels around 10-150 ng/L. Salts are left unaffected, so in the following time series of the demo activities are reported only TOC, bisphenol and alkylphenols. Time profiles of the concentrations of these contaminants during demo activities in September and October 2022 are reported in Figure 10 and Figure 11, respectively. The TOC is abated under 1 mg/L from 8.5 mg/L, on average. The presence of alkylphenols and bisphenol A in the input water is always under the 300 ng/L guidance limits promulgated by EU for the contaminants of concern in drinking water (Directive (EU) 2020/2184) and very limited. The PHOTO.CAT submodule is able to eliminate these compounds below MQL (7 and 18 ng/L for bisphenol A and alkylphenols, respectively).

The data reported demonstrate that the PHOTO.CAT submodule is able to eliminate non-biodegradable and hazardous organic compounds, retaining the levels of sulphates. Average composition of the PHOTO.CAT waters produced during Demo activities is reported in Table 6. The water so purified, eventually mixed with NF1/NF2 water to achieve the desired composition, is being used in dyeing baths to recover sulfates.

Figure 10. Time profiles of TOC, Bisphenol A and alkylphenols in before and after PHOTO.CAT treatment, September 2022.

Figure 11. Time profiles of TOC, Bisphenol A and alkylphenols in before and after PHOTO.CAT treatment, October 2022.

7.1.1 Energy footprint per unit water produced

The PHOTO.CAT submodule can be run in continuous mode with UV-LED backup source activated when UV solar light is not sufficiently intense, or in solar mode only (operations stop when solar UV < 15 W/m²). In solar mode only the energy footprint per m³ water purified is 1.5 kWh. This allows to consider the project objective QO2 is achieved in Demosite4.

7.2 NF1 and NF2 submodules

NF1 submodule is equipped with three high permeability nanofiltration thin film membranes with MW cutoff for neutrals around 150-300 Da. Rejection of divalent and multivalent ions is very high (MgSO₄ > 98%). Rejection of monovalent ions depends on concentration and decreases with its increase. Typical flow rates of permeate are 7 m³/day per membrane (around 20 m³/day with the three membranes mounted).

NF2 submodule is equipped with a thin film nanofiltration membrane with MW cutoff for neutrals under 150 Da. Rejection of chlorides and other similar size monovalent ions is > 90%. The two cartridges can sustain an average permeate production of 10 m³/day.

The two NF units can be remotely controlled (Figure 12) and are fed with a slightly pressurized water line from the outlet of the biological WWTP plant (after sand filtering) and run in continuous mode, with a production capacity of 20 and 10 m³/day of NF1 and NF2 treated water, respectively. Treated waters are stored in proper tanks before use.

Figure 12. Direct and Remote-control console of NF1 and NF2 submodules.

Water compositions before and after treatment during Demo activities are reported from Figure 13 to Figure 16. Main features are:

- 1) More than 80% TOC abatement with both NF1 and NF2 treatments (Figure 13), achieving the goal of non-biodegradable TOC abatement. The concentrations of bisphenol A and alkylphenols are both under MQL in the treated water.
- 2) Both NF1 and NF2 eliminate sulfates > 98% (Figure 14). Besides sulfate, also divalent and multivalent cations are eliminated, with softening of the treated waters.
- 3) NF2 achieves nearly complete demineralization (see Figure 15 for chloride rejection and Figure 16 for specific conductivity decrease).

Overall, from NF1 and NF2 are obtained:

A – 20 m³/day of low TOC, low sulfates, softened water from NF1

B – 10 m³/day of low TOC, nearly demineralized water from NF2.

The average NF1 and NF2 water compositions during demo activities are reported in Table 6.

Figure 13. TOC time profiles at the inlet and at the outlet of NF1 and NF2 during Demo operations, months October – November 2022.

Figure 14. Sulphates time profiles at the inlet and at the outlet of NF1 and NF2 during Demo operations, months October – November 2022.

Figure 15. Chlorides time profiles at the inlet and at the outlet of NF1 and NF2 during Demo operations, months October – November 2022.

Figure 16. Specific Conductivity time profiles at the inlet and at the outlet of NF1 and NF2 during Demo operations, months October – November 2022.

7.2.1 High salinity ground water demineralization

To have an alternative source of water available in case of mains water supply problems, the NF1 and NF2 were also tested in the demineralization of a brackish well water drawn from a well below the Galeb facility. This water cannot be directly used due to a hardness exceeding 200 °F and a conductivity higher than 12 mScm⁻¹. The chloride content is of the order of 4 g/L (composition data are reported in Table 4). On 12 October a purification test was run on this well water by using NF1 and NF2. NF1 was run at 20 m³/day of permeate, NF2 at 10 m³/day. Performances of NF2 can be enhanced by using NF1 permeate as input water. The average composition of the NF1 and NF2 permeates are reported in Table 5.

NF1 treatment achieves a completely softened water, the hardness is under 2 °F from 240 °F of the feed water. Chloride (and sodium) rejection is only around 40% due to the high saline content. However, this water can be used in washing baths, where the action of nonionic surfactant is slightly enhanced by the presence of a Chaotropic agent like sodium chloride. NF2 treatment led to a softened and slightly mineralized water (chloride rejection > 90%). Even better demineralization can be obtained feeding NF2 with NF1 permeate and optimizing NF2 working parameters for the new feed. Extended membrane lifetime, lower water and energy consumption are achieved.

Parameter	NF1	NF2
pH	6.96	5.12
k (μS cm ⁻¹)	7570	267.3
TC (mg L ⁻¹)	18.1	10.21
IC (mg L ⁻¹)	17.1	9.359
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)	0.9	0.8
TN (mg L ⁻¹)	1.1	0.4
Chlorides (mg L ⁻¹)	2324	71
Nitrates (mg L ⁻¹)	<2	<2
Posphates (mg L ⁻¹)	<2	<2
Sulfates (mg L ⁻¹)	<2	<2
Sodium (mg L ⁻¹)	1304	48
Magnesium (mg L ⁻¹)	<1	<1
Calcium (mg L ⁻¹)	<1	<1

Table 5. Permeate composition of the brackish well water available at the Galeb site

8 Conclusions

The Demo activities on PHOTO.NANOF have completely validated the train of technologies implemented Demosite 4. During these activities, it has been demonstrated that PHOTO.NANOF can produce up to 36 m³ of treated water to be reused in the textile facilities (washing, dyeing and bleaching baths). Three different types of tertiary treated waters are produced, whose average compositions during demo activities are reported in Table 6. Waters are mixed accordingly to the compositions required by the reuse (dyeing, washing or bleaching baths). Main features of the three types of purified waters are:

- 1) PHOTO.CAT: low TOC, organic micropollutants under 20 ng/L. Salt content retained.
- 2) NF1: low TOC, organic micropollutants under 20 ng/L. Water softened with divalent and multivalent ions eliminated.
- 3) NF2: low TOC, organic micropollutants under 20 ng/L. Divalent and multivalent ions eliminated, > 80% elimination of monovalent ions like chlorides.

Compared with an average consumption of 165 m³/day of tap water, the reuse of 36 m³ /day achieved with PHOTO.NANOF reduces by 22% the water footprint of Galeb dd company.

Parameter	From			
	WWTP	PHOTO.CAT	NF1	NF2
pH	7.9	8.3	7.1	6.7
k ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	3675	3789	180	10
TC (mg L^{-1})	30.4	25.7	18.5	4.4
IC (mg L^{-1})	21	24	17	3.1
TOC (mg L^{-1})	9.4	0.98	1.1	1
TN (mg L^{-1})	1			
Chlorides (mg L^{-1})	65	71	48	2.5
Nitrates (mg L^{-1})	3.5			
Posphates (mg L^{-1})	<0.1			
Sulfates (mg L^{-1})	1270	1352	<2	<2
Sodium (mg L^{-1})	610	25	21	2.2
Magnesium (mg L^{-1})	18	19.8	<1	<1
Calcium (mg L^{-1})	50	35	<1	<1
Bisphenol A (ng L^{-1})	35	<MQL	<MQL	<MQL
Octyl and nonylphenol (ng L^{-1})	120	<MQL	<MQL	<MQL

Table 6. Average water compositions obtained after PHOTO.CAT, NF1 or NF2 tertiary treatments during Demo activities at Galeb dd Demosite. Data in the first column report the composition of the input water coming from the biological WWTP (Table 3).

In conclusion, PHOTO.NANOF is a flexible and adaptable suite of tertiary treatments that allows reuse of water in an industrial environment, in this case implementation is done in a textile company. Beside water reuse, also salts reuse is achieved. Technical and operational KPI 12 to 30, regarding water quality, reported in D6.1 (Project Ô “Set of Key Performance Indicators”) are achieved, in particular KPI 26 (micropollutants), KPI 12 (BOD) and KPI 29 (sulphates). In terms of quantitative objectives, PHOTO.NANOF contributes to QO1, namely reach a 30% reduction of Water Footprint of industrial sites at Project Ô level.

9 Appendix

9.1 LC-MS-MS method for pesticide, bisphenol A, octyl and nonylphenols detection and quantification

9.1.1 Sample Preparation with Stir Bar Sorptive Extraction (SBSE)

Samples were prepared by aliquoting 100 mL of water into 150 mL glass stoppered flasks. 8 g of salt (NaCl) was added to each sample; once the salt had dissolved, a SBSE magnet with 100 micron PDMS phase was introduced in the water sample. The samples were placed on a magnetic stirrer for 3 hours at 700 rpm. The SBSE magnet were transferred in an Eppendorf with 200 µl of solvent (H₂O:MeOH 50:50) for 30 minutes in order to desorb the analytes.

9.1.2 LC-MS-MS analysis

The extracts were analysed by a HPLC-ESI-MS-MS (triple quadrupole) model LCMS-8045 Shimadzu. The chromatographic conditions are reported in Table 7 and the gradient elution profile is reported in Figure 17. The parameters of the ESI interface are reported in Table 8. A total of 157 pesticides, bisphenol A, octyl and nonylphenols were analysed in MRM by using the transitions reported in Table 9. The Figure 18 reports the MRM chromatograms of a 10 µg/l standard. Concerning pesticides, MQL is lower than 0.02 µg/l for all pesticides, 0.007 µg/l for bisphenol A, 0.018 µg/l for octyl and nonylphenol.

Column:	Raptor Biphenyl 2.7 um 10 x 2.1 mm
Eluents:	A: 0.2% formic acid and 2 mM ammonium formate in water B: 0.2% formic acid and 2 mM ammonium formate in Methanol
Gradient Program:	
	Time (min) Conc. B (%)
	0 30
	35 80
	39 100
	42.5 100
	43 30
Flow (ml/min):	0.2
Column Temperature (°C)	40
Injection Volume (ul)	20

Table 7. LC conditions for the analysis of the pesticides, bisphenol A and alkylphenols

Figure 17. Gradient profile of the LC-MS analysis.

Interface:	ESI
Nebulizing Gas Flow (l/min):	3
Heating Gas Flow (l/min):	10
Interface Temperature (°C):	300
Desolvation Temperature (°C):	520
DL Temperature (°C):	250
Heat block Temperature (°C):	400
Drying Gas Flow (l/min):	10

Table 8. ESI interface parameters.

Compound name	m/z	event 1	event 2	Ret. Time
Acetamiprid	223.2	126.1	56.2	12.14
ACLONIFEN	265	182	218	32.081
ACRINATHRIN	559	208	181	40.331
AMETOCTRADIN	276	176	149	28.959
Ametrina	228.1	68.1	186.1	16.397
Atrazine	215.9	174.1	104.1	16.012
ATRAZINE DESETHYL	188	104	146	6.014
Atrazine-Desisopropyl	174	104.1	96.1	3.884
AZIMSULFURON	425	182	156	28.685
Azoxystrobin	404	329.1	344.1	32.233
Benalaxyl	326.2	148.2	208.2	33.278
Bifenazate	301.2	198.1	170.1	29.18
Bisphenol A	227.1	133.1	212.1	25.64
BIXAFEN	414	394	266	29.614
Boscalid	343.1	307.1	140.1	27.049
Bromacil	261	205.5	204.4	11.947
Bupirimate	317.1	166.1	237.2	27.76
Buprofezin	306.2	106.1	86.2	34.315
Cadusafos	271.1	159.1	97	31.022
Carbaryl	202.1	145.1	127.1	16.344
Carbendazim	192.1	160.1	132.1	3.535

Carbofuran	222.3	165.1	123.1	15.626
Carfentrazone-ethyl	429.1	412	346	31.584
Chloemerquat	122	63.1	58.2	1.654
Chlorantraniliprole	484	452.9	286	25.41
Chloridazon	222	92.2	104.1	7.6
Chlorotoluron	212.9	72.1	46.1	15.198
Clodimafox-Propargyl	349.9	266.1	91.2	33.167
CLODINAFOX F.A.	312	266	91	25.626
Clomazone	240	125.1	89	23.433
Clopyralid	192	145.9	109.9	3.589
Cloquintocet-Mexyl	336.1	192.1	238.1	37.786
Clothianidin	250	169.1	113.1	5.424
Cyazofamid	325.1	108.1	44.2	30.999
Cycloxydim	326	280.2	180.2	36.1
Cyflufenamid	413	295.2	241	33.551
Cymoxanil	199	128.1	111.2	8.202
Cyproconazole	291.9	70.1	125	24.045
Cyprodinil	226.1	77.1	93.1	26.012
Cyprosulfamide	375.6	135.1	121.2	21.15
Cyromazine	167.1	68.1	43.1	1.82
Daminozide	160.9	142.5	142.4	1.915
Diazinon	304.9	169.2	96.9	30.765
Diclobutrazol	327.5	70.1	159.1	28.911
Difenoconazole	406.1	251.1	152	36.111
Diflubenzuron	311.1	158.1	141.1	27.978
Diflufenicam	395.1	266.2	245.9	33.552
Dimethenamid	275.6	244.1	168.1	26.013
Dimethoate	230.2	199	125	6.997
Dimethoate	229.9	199.1	125.1	7.268
Dimethomorph	388.2	301.1	165.1	30.71
Diuron	233	94.1	137.1	20.878
DODINE	228	60	57	24.751
Emamectin benzoate	872.3	158.2	82	36.696
Emamectin benzoate1	886.4	158.2	82.2	37.345
Epoxiconazole	329.9	121.1	101.1	29.924
Ethiofencarb	225.9	107.1	164.1	17.113
Ethirimol	210.2	140.2	98.1	6.898
Fenamidone	312.1	92.1	236.2	26.339
Fenbuconazole	337	125.1	70.1	30.929
Fenhexamid	302.1	97.2	55.2	25.41
Fenothiocarb	254.1	72.1	160.1	31.135
Fenoxaprop-P-Ethyl	362.1	288.1	121.2	36.645
Fenoxycarb	302.2	116.1	88.1	30.761
Fenoxycarb	301.9	88.1	116.2	30.767
Fenpropidin	274.1	147.2	117.1	23.546
FENPYRAZAMINE	332	230	304	29.039
Flonicamid	230.1	203.1	148.1	3.567
Florasulam	360	129.1	192	19.95
Fluazinam_neg	462.9	415.8	397.8	34.536
Flufenacet	364.1	152.1	194.2	28.548

Fluopicolide	383	173.1	109.1	27.052
Fluoxypyr	255	209.1	181.1	10.485
Flusilazole	315.9	247.2	165.1	30.167
Fluxapyroxad	380.1	247.9	131	25.578
Furathiocarb	383.2	195.1	252.1	37.947
Heptenophos	251	127	108.9	20.661
Hexaconazole	314.3	70.1	159	27.76
Hexythiazox	353.1	228.1	168.1	38.629
Imidacloprid	256.1	175.1	209.1	9.901
Indoxacarb	527.9	150.1	203	37.026
Indoxacarb	527.9	149.9	203	37.13
Iprovalicarb	321	119.2	144.1	25.413
Isoproturon	207	72.1	46.2	17.662
Isoxaben	333.7	165.1	150.1	29.212
Isoxadifen-Ethyl	312.9	232.3	203.9	33.266
Lufenuron	511	141.1	158.3	35.008
Mandipropamid	412	328.1	125	30.417
Mepanipyrim	224.1	77.1	106.1	27.433
Mesosulfuron-Methyl	503.8	182.2	83.1	28.19
Metalaxyl	280.2	220.2	192.2	23.049
Metamitron	202.9	175.3	104	7.769
Metconazole	320	70.2	125.1	29.399
Methalaxyl-M	280	220.2	192.2	23.097
Methidathion	302.9	145	85.1	26.016
Methiocarb	225.9	169.1	107.1	17.168
Methiocarb-Sulfone	274.6	122.2	201	11.464
Methiocarb-Sulfoxide	241.9	185.2	122.1	9.581
Methomyl	162.9	88.1	106.1	4.55
Methoxyfenozide	369	313.2	149.1	28.087
Metobromuron	259	148	170	16.399
Metrafenone	408.9	209.2	227.1	35.522
Metribuzin	215.1	187.2	131.1	13.396
Metsulfuron-Methyl	381.9	199.1	167.2	23.11
Molinate	187.9	83.2	126.2	24.75
Myclobutanil	289.1	70.1	125	26.066
Nicosulfuron	411	182.2	213.1	22.808
4-nonylphenol	219.1	133.1	147.1	36.57
4-octylphenol	205.1	106.1		35.21
Oxadixyl	279.1	219.2	132.1	18.817
Oxamyl	236.9	72.1	90.1	4.47
Paclobutrazol	294.1	70.2	125.1	22.898
Paraoxon-Methyl	248	109.1	201.9	14.326
Penconazole	284.1	70.1	159	28.635
Pendimethalin	282.1	212.2	194.2	33.154
Pethoxamid	296	131.2	91.2	29.642
Phenmedipham	318.2	108.1	93.1	22.68
Phosphamidon	299.5	126.9	174.2	15.263
Picoxystrobin	368.1	145.1	205.1	32.507
Pirimicarb	239	72.1	182.2	11.23
Prochloraz	376	308	70.1	33.498

Propamocarb	189.2	102.2	144.2	2.381
Propazine	229.9	146.1	188.2	19.852
Propiconazole	341.9	159	69.1	31.897
Propiconazole	342.1	159	69.2	32.295
Propoxur	209.9	111.1	168.1	13.869
Prosulfuron	419.9	141.2	167.1	28.409
Pyraclostrobin	388	194.1	163.1	36.33
Pyraflufen-Ethyl	412.9	339.1	253.1	32.725
Pyridaphenthion	340.9	189.2	205.1	30.954
Pyrimethanil	200.1	107.1	82.2	18.42
Pyriproxyfen	322.1	96.1	227.1	38.135
Pyroxulam	435.1	195.2	258.1	25.788
Quinalphos	298.6	163.1	147.1	31.133
Quinoxyfen	308	197	162	36.881
Quinalofop-P-Ethyl	372.9	299.2	91	37.608
Simazine	201.9	124.2	132.1	11.747
Spinosad	732.3	142.2	98.2	34.926
Spinosad	732.3	142.2	98.1	35.131
Spiroxamine	298.2	144.2	100.2	21.784
Sulcotrione	345.9	139.1	69	19.177
Tebuconazole	308	70.1	125	27.923
Tebufenozide	353.1	133.1	105.1	29.562
Tebufenpyrad	334.2	117.1	145.1	34.425
Tembotrione	441	341	262.1	27.665
Terbutyn	242	186.2	68.1	20.788
Tetraconazole	372	159	70.1	26.885
Thiacloprid	253.2	126.1	99	15.958
Thiamethoxam	292	211.1	181.1	6.516
Thifensulfuron-Methyl	388.1	167.1	205.1	22.687
Tolclofos-Methyl	300.9	269.1	175	33.108
Triadimefon	294.1	69.2	197.1	25.63
Triadimenol	296.2	70.2	43.2	22.844
Tri-Allate	304.1	143	86.1	35.325
Trifloxystrobin	409	186.1	206.1	35.807
Trinexapac-Ethyl	252.9	69.1	207.2	23.439
Triticonazole (alios)	190.1	163.1	136.1	18.804
Zoxamide	336	187	159	28.579

Table 9. MRM transition used in the HPLC-ESI-MS-MS of the 157 pesticides, bisphenol A, octyl- and nonylphenol.

Figure 18. Chromatograms of the MRM events for 157 pesticides plus Bis phenol A, p-nonylphenol and p-octylphenol.